

Predicting Demand and Supply in a Real-Time Traffic Management Framework

Athina Tympakianaki¹[0000-0001-7818-1292], Mohammadmahdi Rahimiasl²[0000-0002-0421-8651], Charis Chalkiadakis³[0000-0002-5605-8784], Monica Dominguez¹[0000-0001-6253-0670], Ynte Vanderhoydonc²[0000-0001-6835-3302], Jordi Casas¹[0000-0002-7110-8751], Eleni I. Vlahogianni³[0000-0002-2423-5475], Siegfried Merceles²[0000-0001-9355-6566]

¹ Aimsun SLU, Ronda Universitat 22B, Barcelona 08007, Spain

² University of Antwerp – imec, IDLab - Faculty of Applied Engineering, Sint-Pietersvliet 7, 2000 Antwerp, Belgium

³ National Technical University of Athens, 5 Iroon Polytechniou Str., Zografou Campus, 15773 Athens, Greece

Abstract. Predicting the future supply and demand of a transport network are challenging and important problems in real-time traffic management systems that are essential to enhance the decision-making process for deploying adequate traffic strategies under different conditions (e.g., road works, accidents). In the context of the TANGENT H2020 project, simulation-based and data-driven methodologies are developed focusing on the real-time demand and supply prediction problems. This paper focuses on the development and integration of the demand and supply models as well as incident detection methods into traffic simulation environments for network-wide traffic predictions. The role of each component of the framework and their interoperability is explained in the paper, using as testbed the network of Athens, Greece.

Keywords: Intelligent Transport Systems, Traffic simulation, Demand and Supply Traffic predictions, Anomaly detection, Deep learning

1 Introduction

Traffic prediction has more than 30 years of history, yet a challenging problem, fragmented in terms of methodologies and tools implemented for real-time traffic management systems. Traditional parametrical approaches for traffic prediction present limitations when capturing the spatial and temporal relationships of traffic patterns, hence, there is a need to develop more advanced data-driven methods for predicting the future traffic supply and demand. Furthermore, the role of traffic simulation is very important as it captures the demand and supply interactions within the transport ecosystem. This work focuses on the development and integration of demand and supply methods into traffic simulation environments for traffic predictions.

2 Framework for real-time traffic monitoring and forecasting

Fig. 1 depicts the integration process and workflow between the demand and supply models with the simulation environment. The first step involves the collection and preparation of the traffic data that are fed to the demand and supply components. The supply

component consists of data-driven traffic prediction models as well as traffic simulation models. The selection of the most adequate supply prediction model and their interaction depend on the scope of the application. For instance, data-driven models can be applied for local traffic predictions where historical and real-time traffic measurements are available for specific locations. Simulations can be performed for predicting the network-wide traffic conditions, covering also locations for which real traffic observations are not available. The demand is a key input to transport simulation models, along with information on the traffic supply. In offline transport applications (e.g., design and evaluation of response plans), the estimation of a base demand, representing average historical travel patterns and specific circumstances (e.g., recurrent congestion, special event), is needed to simulate and assess the network-wide conditions. In online applications, data-driven models can be trained for predicting the future demand, adapting the base demand to real-time traffic conditions. The output of the real-time local traffic prediction models can be used as input into the demand prediction component. Subsequently, network-wide simulation can be performed to predict adequate network performance metrics (travel times, speeds, flows, etc.). Besides the demand input, the simulation can incorporate changes in the network supply, such as detected traffic-related incidents or road closures due to an event, to evaluate their impact on the road network. The simulation output can be further fed into the data-driven prediction models by providing additional information to enhance the accuracy and reliability of the local

traffic predictions (e.g., when an incident is identified and its impact is simulated).

Fig. 1. Framework for real-time traffic monitoring and forecasting.

2.1 Data-driven supply predictions methods

Traffic Supply Forecasting

Traffic supply forecasting contributes significantly to anticipating and preventing traffic congestion. The supply side of a transport network can be defined by traffic measurements such as traffic speed, travel time, density, and flow. Traffic supply forecasting has been tackled from different modeling perspectives during the last few years. Among various approaches, data-driven approaches have shown excellent results with the rise of data collection and computational resources. The state-of-the-art (SotA) models in

deep learning utilize Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Attention Mechanisms. By benchmarking different SotA models, optimizing their hyper-parameters, and performing an in-depth fusion of multiple models for the examined case study (described in Section 3), Multivariate Time Series Forecasting with GNN (MTGNN) [1] is shown to be one of the best models for this task. The method uses graph learning layer, Graph Convolutional Networks and Temporal CNNs to capture latent dependencies in spatial and temporal contexts. The entire framework is trained in an end-to-end manner.

Incident detection

Incident detection is defined as the detection of extreme traffic conditions caused by, e.g., an accident or nonrecurrent high traffic volumes. Early detection is crucial for timely activation of adequate response plans aiming to alleviate the impacts and returning the traffic conditions back to normal. Incident detection methods detect nonrecurrent congestion by comparing the current traffic state with the predictions. When the measurements deviate significantly from the predicted values, an anomaly is detected.

The deviation is measured through different statistics (such as absolute or squared error, z-scores). In the next step, isolation forest [2], which is an unsupervised machine learning model, is used to aggregate all those anomaly scores into a unified anomaly score. The algorithm works by isolating observations by randomly selecting one initially calculated anomaly score, and then randomly selecting a split value between the maximum and minimum values of the selected one. The unified anomaly score is compared with a prespecified threshold to determine if it's considered an anomaly.

2.2 Demand estimation and prediction methods

Simulation-based demand estimation

Demand estimation refers to the process of adjusting the Origin-Destination (OD) trip matrices of a given transport model, usually using simulation-based approaches. This process is formulated as an optimization problem, aiming to find an OD matrix that best reproduces a set of traffic measurements when assigned to a given network.

In this work, the existing gradient-based algorithm [3], in the Aimsun Next simulation software [4], is used to perform the offline estimation of OD matrices. The approach requires the calculation of the assignment matrix, which maps the contributions of OD flows on links with available traffic counts in the network. Its main advantage is the analytical computation of the gradient of the objective function, which is expected to result in robust solutions. Nevertheless, it is limited to using only traffic counts (due to the assumption about their linear relationship with the OD matrix), which can be problematic for congested networks as this assumption does not hold.

Data-driven demand predictions

Online demand prediction methods are used in the context of real-time traffic management and route guidance, aiming at providing fast estimates for recent time intervals with predictions for future time intervals.

In this work, a preliminary attempt is made in using a GNN architecture to predict aggregated demand generated at origins (in the OD matrix). The proposed approach adapts the work proposed in [5], which spatial-temporal graph attention network (ST-GAT) architecture for traffic supply forecasting to the demand prediction problem. Supervised experiments are carried out to predict the demand at time t (at all origins generating vehicles) using traffic data from the previous hour ($t-1h$) from all sections aggregated in 15-minute intervals. The spatial-temporal components of the ST-GAT architecture allow for modelling both the geometry of the network (spatial) as well as the evolution of flow as a vector of time series from the previous hour in 15-minute intervals (i.e., $t-60$ min, $t-45$ min, $t-30$ min, $t-15$ min as a feature vector and t as the class to be predicted) across the whole network. Synthetic simulated data has been used to test several configurations in a controlled experimental machine learning setting.

3 Application of the framework to a case study

Athens case study

The Athens case study is one of the TANGENT project case studies, which is used as testbed to apply the proposed framework. In particular, the inner-ring urban transportation network of Athens, Greece (Fig. 2) is used, which is calibrated and validated in Aimsun Next using hourly traffic data (counts and speeds) from 2023. The network consists of 860 nodes and 1,856 sections as well as 237 loop detectors. With respect to the calibrated demand, approximately 48,000 vehicles are inserted in the network during morning peak hour (08:00 – 09:00) for a typical day.

Specifically, traffic data was collected for two weeks in 2023; a week with normal operation of the network (February 20th – February 26th) and a week with a known (severe) flooding event (September 11th – September 17th). The collected data was further used as input to the simulation model to perform a series of demand calibration experiments to derive representative OD matrices for both the normal week and the week with the disturbance. The same data set was further used to train the data-driven traffic supply forecasting as well as the incident detection models. Following the framework workflow (Fig. 1), the adjusted OD matrices and traffic predictions can be used to train the data-driven demand model, which in a real-time context can provide the future demand as input to simulation for deriving the network-wide traffic conditions.

In this work, due to space limitation, preliminary results are shown from the application of the data-driven traffic supply forecasting (local predictions), incident detections and the demand calibrations for different traffic patterns.

Fig. 2. Athens simulation testbed.

3.1 Preliminary results

Traffic predictions and anomaly detection results

The trained model, which considers 1-hour predictions and a test set including both normal and event days, has an accuracy MAE of 5.57 km/h. Usually, a MAE of around 3 km/h is expected for 1-hour predictions, but since half of the testing is done on a period where the network was not functioning normally, the achieved performance is expected. For every sensor, a graph with anomaly scores is constructed. Fig. 3 depicts anomaly scores for the different select days described in the previous section. Red points are anomalies, while blue points are normal scores. The contamination threshold is set at 5%. This implies that the thresholds are determined such that 5% of the data is classified as anomalous. However, certain anomalies, specifically those where the predicted traffic speed is lower than the observed traffic speed, are not of interest to our analysis. Consequently, these specific anomalies are not flagged, resulting in a final anomaly percentage that is less than the initial 5% threshold. The figure shows that the red dots only occurred during event days. As explained in Section 1, anomalies are detected by comparing the predicted with the observed traffic speed (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Anomaly scores over days for a specific sensor for the Athens case study.

Fig. 4. Predicted versus observed values for a specific sensor. Yellow lines are anomalies.

Demand estimation results

For the demand estimations, simulation-based experiments were executed for the normal week and the week with the disturbance. For each day of both weeks, extensive morning (06:00 – 12:00) and afternoon (13:00 – 19:00) peak hours are taken into consideration. As a result, 84 hourly OD matrices are adjusted for each week. In terms of the accuracy of the final output, for the normal week, the Root Mean Square Percentage Error (RMSPE) varies between [0.23, 0.34]. For the week with the disturbance, RMSPE varies between [13, 15]. The high RMSPE values, in the latter, are expected considering the fact that a network-wide disturbance (flooding event) is examined, hence, a high value quantifies the error of the adjustment in relation to the baseline values.

4 Conclusions

This paper outlines the developments of various data-driven and simulation-based methods for network supply and demand predictions, integrated into a framework for real-time traffic management. Preliminary results and insights are provided through the case study of Athens, focusing on data-driven traffic (local) predictions and incident detection. Ongoing work continues on training and testing a demand prediction model, for enhancing the demand input to the simulation model for network-wide predictions. Hybrid data-driven and simulation predictions are also examined, by performing simulations that reproduce identified incidents and providing the simulation outputs as additional information to the data-driven traffic predictions under non-recurrent events.

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